

Time Dependent Schrodinger Equation and Coarse Graining Time

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The time dependent Schrodinger equation contains both x and t and gives the impression of describing evolution in time, just as Newton's second law yields $x(t)$, but we argue that this does not seem to be the case. Rather the explicit time variable seems to be linked with how ordered (sharp frequency) the system has. Even in the case of a free particle $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$, velocity does not appear explicitly (although it may be obtained from E and p). It seems that t and x are described as independent variables, while time evolution requires $x(t)$. Thus, it appears to be deceptive to think that one has time evolution simply because t and x appear in the same equation. If the equation is separable in the two variables, as it is in some cases of the time dependent Schrodinger equation (single bound particle, free particle) there is no $x(t)$ relationship. $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle indicates probability in space which implies a loss of information about $x(t)$. The sign of p , however, indicates a breaking of spatial symmetry or a direction in space. This is, however, associated with a built-in probability, so even knowing velocity v , only describes average motion. Using $\exp(ipx)$ in interaction problems such as one dimensional reflection/refraction brings in more time graining because one needs to establish a kind of steady state picture. Thus, there is an arrow of time and a specific initial direction and reflected direction, but the steady stream picture requires quite a few particles to establish probabilities for reflection/refraction. It is really an average kind of picture which suggests a coarse graining of time rather than actual time evolution. This is with $\exp(-iEt)$ pulled out of the picture showing that the t in this function is something completely different.

A single particle bound state is an even more coarse grained picture to the point of coarse graining out forward and backward motion, an essential part of time evolution. This is again associated with an average in time which is all that is needed to establish E_n (energy) values, but does not describe the dynamics of the problem accurately. In the high E_n limit, the particle either moves to the right or left and the quantum bound picture, being a coarse grained average, does not demonstrate this. Furthermore, if one considers a superposition of bound states with $\exp(-iE_n t)$ weights, i.e. $W = \sum_n a(n)\exp(-iE_n t) W_n$, where W_n is the n th bound state with time coarse graining, then each W_n should correspond to different time coarse graining and one has an evolution of density W^*W which incorporates different coarse graining periods and only describes a kind of average density change, with each coarse graining interval mapping into the same t point which is considered to change according to $\exp(-iE_n t)$.

We consider some of these ideas in this note.

Coarse Graining in Classical Physics

Classical solutions $x(t)$ follow from the solution of Newton's second law (which may also be obtained from a Lagrangian). Given an initial $x_0=x(t_0)$, one may follow the particle in time, so there is exact time evolution. Even in Newtonian mechanics, however, one may have an equation exhibiting coarse graining and dropping time evolution. In particular, a conservation of energy is an example:

$$.5m v^2 + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

One may solve for $v(x)$ (velocity), but there are two solutions \pm and no time and so one has coarse grained over a cycle in the case of a bound particle. In other words, one has lost important information about time evolution and only knows the magnitude of velocity values at each x . It is the energy equation, however, which is associated with a Hamiltonian which describes time evolution in quantum mechanics, and so one may expect already that there are issues with such a time evolution.

Quantum Free Particle

Quantum mechanics makes use of both t and x variables, but they are often treated as independent as in the free particle case or single particle bound case. In such situations, t does not represent time evolution because it is completely detached from x . A free particle is described by:

$$\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

The sign of p indicates the direction of motion in space, i.e. there is spatial symmetry breaking. Using E and p , one may obtain v (both relativistically and nonrelativistically) and so in a sense obtain a kind of time evolution. This, however, is an average time evolution. The term $\exp(-iEt)$ demonstrates a sharp frequency in time, i.e. high order, for a large E . A smaller value of E implies less order. Thus, frequency in time is a measure of energy order or precision, it seems, and not time evolution.

((2)) or in particular $\exp(ipx)$ describes a probability to be at different x values. As a result, even though p and v are sharp values, the particle does not move according to $x(t)$, but rather has a probabilistic dynamic (two dimensional) motion because $\exp(ipx)$ is complex.. This is physically manifest in a two slit experiment. Thus, there is no exact time evolution in the free particle case. The uncertainty in spatial motion is amplified, in a sense, by an interaction with a two slit apparatus and gives rise to the interference term:

$$W(r) = \exp(i p_1 \cdot r) + \exp(i p_2 \cdot r) \quad \text{where } p_1, p_2 \text{ have the same magnitude } p \quad ((3))$$

Even though a single particle interferes, one requires many particles to establish the interference pattern, thus there is again a big coarse graining, we argue, if one wishes to establish $W^*(r)W(r)$.

In a sense there is an arrow of time because a particle with p moves in a certain direction and one may even know its velocity, but time information is lost in the interference picture which aims at describing a pattern which occurs due to many particles, i.e. a coarse grained interval. One does not worry about time differences when adding the two terms of ((3)) as this is already linked with coarse graining.

Quantum Free Particle and Reflection/Refraction

To see the inherent coarse grained behaviour, even in $\exp(ipx)$, one may consider another kind of interaction, namely that of one dimensional reflection/refraction. There is a direction in space given by p , but the interaction again leads to coarse graining as one does not know if the particle reflects or refracts. The solution describes a steady state picture, which like the two slit interference scenario requires many particles. Thus, it seems that time coarse graining is required. One may match:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ ((3a)) and}$$

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - Bp \exp(-ipx) = Cp2 \exp(ip2x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ ((3b))}$$

It seems that there is averaging over many interactions, i.e. a coarse graining of time. Such a quantum picture does not describe individual time evolution. The same is true of the 2-slit experiment. It seems meaningless to ask through what slit the particle passed when using such a probabilistic approach with large time coarse graining that does not even allow one to distinguish time evolution sharply.

Infinite Well Potential

The solution for an infinite well potential is $\sin(kave x)$ where $kave$, i.e. an average, means that one may actually measure different k values. Nevertheless, for high $kave$ values, there should be motion to the right followed by motion to the left and this is not reflected in the solution $\sin(kave x)$ or rather $\sin(kave x) = 1/2i (\exp(ikave x) - \exp(-ikave x))$. The fact that one uses $\exp(ikave x)$, however, indicates that one does not really have time evolution resolution as $\exp(ikave x)$ is really made of a superposition of all $\exp(ipx)$ s and these are associated with different velocities, i.e. time evolution. Thus, the quantum picture seems to be one that is dependent on a coarse grained scenario which in turn is an average one which is quite far from any actual time evolution.

Single Particle Bound State

Coarse graining seems to reach further extremes in the case of a single particle bound state. Like with the classical case, a conservation of energy equation is used, but as argued above, this coarse graining over the time during which the particle is moving forward and then backwards. Important time evolution information is erased as both forward and backward motion may be included. The same holds for the quantum case because $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and $a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ are included in the wavefunction with $a(p)=a(-p)$ or $a(p)=-a(-p)$. In other words, one coarse grains out forward and backwards motion, but this is physical time evolution.

If one considers the correspondence principle, then a high E_n time dependent Schrodinger equation should match a classical picture, but it doesn't because the energy conservation scenario does not separate out forward and backwards motion, which are physically distinct. Thus, using a quantum bound state already implies a coarse grained time interval, but this is not

quantified. Each E_n should have a corresponding coarse grained time interval, but such information is completely lost in:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_n a(n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x) \quad ((4))$$

In such a case, different coarse grained times (representing averaged forwards and backwards motion) are listed with a time weight $\exp(-iE_n t)$ which only depends on the value of energy. As a result, one obtains a time dependent density:

$$\text{density}(t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t) \quad ((5))$$

, but this is not clear time evolution because forward and backwards motion are averaged together with different coarse grained times being treated the same as the entire weight of motion is $\exp(-iE_n t)$ which is dependent on binding energy. In other words, we argue that ((5)) represents some kind of coarse grained picture. The time dependence seems to be linked more to how tightly bound the average system is than to any real time evolution of a particle. $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$, however, is already a pattern which would require a lot of measurements to establish its form and so is also about how a particle is bound in space with $\exp(-iE_n t)$ describing how it is bound in time, which does not seem to be linked to time evolution. The fact that the density changes in time seems to suggest changes in time in the tightness of binding, not in the time evolution of a single particle in space. Thus, it is irrelevant to binding if the one W_{n1} represents more coarse grained time than W_{n2} .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics, being probabilistic, loses some information about time evolution, even in the simplest case of a free particle $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$. If an interaction occurs, such as a two slit interaction or one dimensional reflection/refraction, matters get worse because one deals with $\exp(ipx)$ type probabilities and ignores time altogether. Patterns emerge which require multiple particle interactions, hence large coarse grained time intervals. For example, a single particle undergoes interference, but many particles are required to establish the interference pattern. A single particle reflects or refracts, but multiple particles are required to establish the probabilities for these. Thus, we suggest there is coarse graining of time associated with quantum mechanics.

This coarse graining because pronounced in single particle bound states which are based on a Schrodinger equation which includes a Hamiltonian or energy term. Such a term already coarse grains out forwards and backwards motion classically and does the same quantum mechanically. The objective is to find E_n which describes how tightly bound the particle is. $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ describes spatial density which requires a lot of measurement to be established and so does not really describe dynamics.

We argue that these features carry over into the supposed time evolution picture of $W = \sum_n a(n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$. Here each W_n represents a different coarse grained interval, we argue, but this is completely ignored in the expression. Time is only linked with how tightly bound the particle is. Thus, a changing density (in time) $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ simply shows that the

system is more or less tightly bound in time and does not seem to have anything to do with physical time evolution of a single particle. The density $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ already is quite coarse grained and eliminates time evolution and so $W(x,t)$ simply builds on this coarse graining.